

LINGUAPRAGMATIC AND LINGUOLOGICAL STUDY OF LITOTES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19104844>

ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the research of one stylistic device – litotes from the point of linguapragmatic aspect in both English and Uzbek languages. Litotes improves the meaning of words and phrases as a way of discrimination, focusing on specific events by reducing their signs. In this sense, litotes is opposed to hyperbole, which is why it is also called “reverse hyperbole”. Moreover, the background analysis of litotes, its usage, meaning and functions are analysed on a pragmatic basis. In order to explore some examples of litotes, some methods are used such as data collection, data organization, data analysis as well as interpretation and comparison. Differences and similarities are revealed relying on linguapragmatic features in both languages. All examples of litotes given in the article are taken from speeches, prominent novels and epic poems in Uzbek and English in order to identify litotes.

Keywords: *litotes, meiosis, hyperbole, understatement, double negation, contradiction*

INTRODUCTION

In world linguistics, the main focus is not only on the semantics of the word, but also on the relationship between the word and the speech of a particular subject, its pragmatic content, evaluation and relationship. Litotes is often used in fiction, poetry to enhance the descriptive and (values, religion, knowledge of previous generations) and rapidly developing modern phenomena in the mass culture of our generation (clips, videos, computer games, etc.), between elite and popular culture.

Learning foreign languages is becoming more relevant, since university graduates and employees who speak foreign languages are becoming increasingly in demand from employers. All of the above creates the need to reconsider the goals and objectives of teaching. Foreign languages, as well as to create a modern teaching methodology. Litotes is an artistic concept.

Wouden's distinction between understanding litotes as logical double negations, and as a synonym for understatement or meiosis. Whereas the view that litotes can be seen as meiosis is shared by Haverkate and Lanham and among those who equate litotes with double negation is, for example, de Swart, On the other hand, Neuhaus claims that litotes and meiosis are distinct notions, while Yuan argues that the figure is simply “often confused with meiosis and understatement”.

METHODOLOGY

To conduct this comparative study, an in-depth qualitative content analysis approach was utilized. This method allowed for a systematic and detailed examination of the litotes in both English and Uzbek languages. The following steps were taken to ensure a thorough analysis of the data:

Data Collection: in order to observe various sources, this method was used to collect comprehensive data on litotes in English and Uzbek. The sources included reputable academic

articles published in linguistics journals, and online language resources, such as dictionaries and language learning platforms.

Data Organization: The collected data were organized according to the structure, function, and usage of litotes in both languages. This organization facilitated a systematic comparison and analysis of the litotes across the two languages.

Data Analysis: The information were analyzed by comparing the structure, function, and usage of litotes in English and Uzbek. The analysis aimed to identify similarities and differences between the two languages in terms of the types of litotes, their functions, and the contexts in which they are used.

Interpretation and Comparison: The results of the data analysis were interpreted in the context of the broader linguistic and cultural differences between English and Uzbek.

According to the “Merriam-Webster” dictionary, litotes is “understatement in which an affirmative is expressed by the negative of the contrary (as in “not a bad singer” or “not unhappy”)” and it is actually meant to say less than one. This definition applies to sentences such as: “*Tom is not unhappy*”.

A crucial study of litotes has been offered by Hoffmann, who highlights its argumentative functions but refers to it using the phrase negation contrary, which stands for “negation of the opposite”.

RESULT AND DISSCUSSIONS

Often in literature and in everyday speech, such deviations are used to turn the rejection of something into morality. An example of this is: “You are not sure you can do the task.” What this means is that the speaker is convinced: the interlocutor cannot perform the task. However, with the help of rejection, he absolutely reflected this. In this case, litotes is a softening used in speech not to openly express your dissatisfaction, but to do it politely.

Bergann points out that by using certain rhetorical device called litotes to express their intentions people describe the object by negating its opposite. Thus, expression which is accepted as litotes is formed by negation plus adjective or noun.

Horn refers that litotes is rhetorical figure that contains a specific use of negative constructions. Inserting not to adjective or adjective with negative affix or noun serves to accomplish a positive merit in a person or thing. However, the positive merit is somehow reduced in quality as compared to the positive expression making a straightforward assertion of positive merit. This is showed in the examples below:

It is not bad thing = It is a good thing

He is no coward = He is a brave man

Yuan classifies litotes to three types. His classification is based on Aristotle’s interpretation of opposition. The philosopher says: “In four ways the things are said to be opposed to each other: as contraries, , as privation, as relative, as possession or as negation and affirmation. Based on this classification, three types of litotes are derived:

1. Contradictory litotes (negation + negation): *Thus, I consent, sir, this Constitution, because I expect no better, and because I am not sure that it is not the best*
2. Contrary (negation + antonym): *My guardian will be awfully keen for you to come and stay with us. He is not half bad when you know him.*
3. Relative (negation + correlation/metonymy): *The class in chaos, but it is not the student’s fault.*

These given examples illustrate the way in which contradictory type of litotes is formed. In litotes is structured by using a negator like not, no, nor. Which indicates contradictory opposite, is usually formed by using a negator “not” and negative-privative preposition like “without”. Contradictory litotes is formed by using a negator paired with negating affixes as “un-, in-, dis-, -less.”

A litotes variation is a construction containing two negations, such as not unlike, not promising, not unhappy, and so on. Two negatives add up to a positive in this case, according to general logical and mathematical concepts. Thus, the litotes may be understood as somewhat like in the sentence: “*Soames, with his lips and his squared chin was somewhat unlike a bull dog*” (*Galsworthy*).

Despite the fact that such constructs make the argument more logically obvious, they are imprecise. They can be considered purposeful understatements, whereas litotes’ pattern structures, for instance, those with only one negative, are considerably more categorical in emphasizing a person’s or thing’s positive quality.

Unlike English, in Uzbek language litotes often comes with hyperbole which is a way of describing something by saying it is much bigger, smaller, and so on and it actually is exaggeration. The large number of examples of hyperbole can be seen in Uzbek epic poem “Alpomish” in order to describe any hero or event. For example: *Shomurti (moylovi) yoqalab haryonga ketgan, ichida sichqonlar*

bolalab ketgan, izidan tushgan pishak ularga olti oyda yetgan.

The definition of litotes in Uzbek is the same with English and often it is used in literature. Examples of litotes come across in many gazelles as well as in famous novels: *Tilimni qichitma, jo’jaxo’roz! Aytmadimmi, kuzda qiyqillab stolning tagiga kirib ketasan, deb... Eh-e, sening xo’roz bo’lishingga hali o’n to’rt prosent bor* (*A.Qahhor*). In this sentence author used the word “jo’jaxo’roz” in order to underestimate the person and to show how much he is powerful than him.

In gazelle written by Uygun, also utilized litotes:

Bu so’zning mazmuni shu qadar issiq,

Quyosh bir kichik sham uning yonida.

Here, he describes that the meaning of the word is the hottest thing as well as the Sun is like a candle in front of the meaning of the word.

In English, litotes is a literary technique that is rarely used in literature. However, it is used in several great literary works to draw the reader's attention and communicate meaning in a subtle way. Here are several literary litotes and how they impact the meaning of the literary work:

Not seldom from the uproar I retired

Into a silent bay, or sportively

Glanced sideways, leaving the tumultuous throng,

To cut across the image of a star

That gleam’d upon the ice... (Prelude: Book 1: Childhood and School. William Wordsworth)

Wordsworth employs litotes in his poetry by combining the phrases “not” and “rarely.” By expressing “not rarely,” the poet indicates that he means “frequently.”

In this approach, he conveys a feeling of understatement about how frequently he withdraws from a crowd or a bustling area to admire visuals and the presence of nature. The use of litotes as a literary device by Wordsworth generates a sense of poetic language and reflection for both the reader and the poet. As a result, by understating how frequently the poet escapes into nature, it really underlines the significance of the deed. The litotes make the escape meaningful to the reader as well.

Moreover, in both languages, litotes is utilized in order to soften the speech and to deliver the idea in indirect way: *This furniture is not good and not appropriate to the room.* In this case, the speaker wanted to express his or her idea gentle, avoiding from saying that is bad and inappropriate, with using negator + positive word, not to upset the listener. Like English, in Uzbek language, such kind of structure is used too: *Bunday qo'pol ohangda gapirish yaxshi emas!*"

CONCLUSION

Litota uses discrimination to improve the meaning of words and phrases, focusing on certain events by decreasing their indicators. It is an inverse hyperbola in this sense. Litotes are fundamentally used for several purposes. One is **ironic emphasis**: by drawing attention to a trait that an object is *not* you are pointing out a trait the object has. Another everyday purpose might be **politeness**. Litotes is a good way to imply meaning without outright saying something rude. The role using litota in figurative language is indispensable in linguistics. Additionally, both in Uzbek and English languages, litotes has the same usage, function as well as meaning.

Both languages make use of litotes as a rhetorical tool to convey politeness, irony, comedy, or to stress a point. In Uzbek, litotes is frequently used in formal circumstances like academic writing or official papers as well as in literature. In English, litotes is typically utilized in casual contexts like social media postings or chats.

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